

Translating e-tourism: localization assessment of tourist promotional website of Novi Pazar

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Abstract

In the tourism industry, e-tourism has led to a growing need for the localization of tourist promotional websites to attract domestic and foreign tourists. This study focuses on the website novipazar.travel, which promotes the city of Novi Pazar in Serbia. Using the skopos theory of translation and tourist profiling based on cultural taxonomies and Serbian statistical analysis, this paper assesses the localization quality of tourism materials and analyses how the destination image of novipazar.travel is localized according to the tourist profiles. The findings show that the website shows high level of localization for domestic tourists, which is not the case for foreign tourists. This study contributes to a better understanding of how to tailor Serbian tourism materials to specific tourist profiles, resulting in more effective promotion.

Keywords: localization, tourist promotional website, Novi Pazar, cultural adaptation

1. Tourism translation and localization

In the field of tourism, there has been much critique on the quality of translated tourism promotional material. Sulaiman and Wilson in their book on translation in tourism (Sulaiman & Wilson, 2019) list many authors who express dissatisfaction with the quality of translation. Duff (1981) made a negative comment on the quality of translation in the tourism industry claiming that the deficiencies in the translations are mostly due to the fact that many texts are translated into the translator's foreign language as opposed to his/her native language. Almost forty years on and the poor quality of TPM translation remains a topic of discussion among scholars as evidenced by the numerous studies that have criticised the translation of tourism related marketing materials (eg. Sumberg, 2004). One of the most recent condemnations appears not within the fraternity of Translation Studies but in the Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research (Standing et al., 2014) indicating that the issue has now caught the attention of scholars outside the field of language. In fact, a survey carried out by Sumberg (2004) suggests that there is agreement among key translation scholars at British universities that the translation standard of tourist promotional material in general is deplorable throughout the world.

Therefore, it is crucial to introduce translation theory to the professional translation of tourist material. Pavlović (Pavlović, 2015) provides an insight of the development of translation processes in the translation industry and its academic understanding. She (ibid.) explains how there was a trend in translation which was based on linguistic equivalence. That means the translator's task was to find a language equivalent from source (ST) to target language (TL). Such approach to translation excluded other aspects of a translated discourse. In the last century, there has been a turn in understanding of translation. It moved away from language equivalence. According to the modern approach, such as functional approach, translators' task is more complex than finding linguistic pairs in SL and TL. Translators' task is now to adopt the material from ST to TL and not just to provide linguistically equivalent term. That turn is incorporated in the functionalistic approach. That approach is focused on the goal or purpose of the material and methodology of fulfilling it adopting it to the TL, audience, channel of communication and culture.

Functionalistic approach is based on the SKOPOS concept (Vermeer, 2012). The concept has always existed in the translation. However, now it has received much more attention than before. It introduces the role of commissioner,

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purpose of the text and analysis of the audience and discourse. Therefore, a translator is not just a finder of linguistic pairs but also much more. A translator's task now is to understand the discourse of the material of ST, to analyse the same discourse in TL and proceed with the adaptation of the material. That understanding is acquired in this paper.

Terms adaptation and localization belong to the idea of translation. The translation approach used in this research belongs to the idea of functionalism. Functionalism acts as a steering instrument – compass in this research. In the field of translation, it was popularized by Vermeer (2012). On the basis it includes the transferring a content from source language (SL) to target language (TL) being focused on achieving the same function as it had in the original text or context. Therefore, translation is more adaptation of the functions of the source content to target audience (their expectations, motivations and habits) to achieve the same effect. The whole communication design is subordinated to that goal -understood as a translation method, Vinay and Darbelnet (Vinay, J. and Darbelnet, 2000) call it adaptation. As it involves much more than a language processing there is another term for it – localisation. Understood in economic, marketing and as a segment of a certain industry it is called localization (Jiménez-Crespo, 2013).

Generally, the whole process of localization and tourism profiles revolves around the concept of push/pull factors and attention value (Sulaiman & Wilson, 2019). Tourists have inner (psychological, sociological, cultural and contextual) elements that force them to travel. Those are push factors. On the other side, there are pull factors or elements of a travel destination that attract the tourists. The attention value represents the potential of the communication element to attract the customer depending on the push-pull effects. The role of the communication specialist and tourism managers is to adopt the communication design so that destination's pull factors overlap as much as possible with targeted tourists' push factors.

This paper sets the layers of cultural and statistical-content analysis of the website novipazar.travel. Before it starts the analysis, it presents statistical data of the tourists who visit Novi Pazar and Serbia as well as their cultural profiles. The tourists are divided in two groups foreign and domestic. As it will be presented in the following parts, domestic tourists are the tourists from Serbia and ex-Yugoslavian countries: Bosnia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Croatia and Slovenia. Foreign tourists have their own language, cultural and statistical features which make them different from the domestic group, as it will be demonstrated through statistics and cultural analysis.

2. Statistical data

The statistical data is collected from three documents issued by the Statistical office of the Republic of Serbia and related offices. They provide the information about the real number of tourists who come to Serbia and Novi Pazar, as well as their lifestyle, habits, way of travelling. Such information is crucial for the adaptation of the tourist material and tourists' websites.

According to the statistical analysis of the Republic of Serbia (Kovacevic, 2023) the number of tourists in Serbia increases gradually through the previous years. In the first quarter of 2023, the number of tourist overnight stays was 2.4 million, which is 16% more than in the first quarter of 2022. As the statistics of Serbia claims (Kovacevic, 2023) in 2023 the three countries whose tourists spent the most nights are the Russian Federation (180.8 thousand), Turkiye (89.3 thousand) and North Macedonia (83.7 thousand). In fourth place in terms of overnight stays are visitors from Bosnia and Herzegovina (68.5 thousand), followed by Romania (58.8 thousand), Montenegro (56.8 thousand) and Bulgaria (53.7 thousand). Overnight stays by tourists from these seven countries make up more than half of the total number of overnight stays realized in the first quarter of 2023. As it can be observed tourists from ex-Yugoslavian countries or domestic tourists: North Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro is the majority of the tourists (200.9 thousand). This trend is followed on the local level in Novi Pazar, except of Russian tourists.

According to the statistical data obtained from the Tourist organization in Novi Pazar (presented in the annex of this paper), in 2022 there were slightly above 20.000 tourists in Novi Pazar in 2022. The tourist from Serbia consisted more than a half of the tourist. If one adds to it the number of tourists from ex-Yugoslavian countries: North Macedonia, Bosnia, Montenegro and Croatia, the number of domestic tourists is over 15000. While the number of foreign tourists is only one quarter of all tourists. The foreign tourists in Novi Pazar are from Turkiye (3 thousand) and Germany (2 thousand).

Considering some closer features of foreign tourist this paper uses the statistical analysis from 2021 as there are no resents (RZS, 2021). Foreign tourists in the Republic of Serbia in 2021 were 41 years old on average. Most of them (60%) were between 25 and 44 years old, followed by those who were between 45 and 64 years old (32%). The results of the survey showed that 50% of foreign tourists have a university degree or more education, 31% have higher education (2 years), while 19% of tourists have secondary or lower level of education. Regarding work status, 85% of foreign tourists were or are employed self-employed, 5% were students, while every tenth tourist was a pensioner, lived on some other income that does not come from employment or was unemployed.

The main reason for visiting Serbia in 2021 was work, which motivated him 36% of all foreign tourists. The second most important reason motivated by 28% of all for foreign tourists it was a holiday. And travel 18%. Among those who came

to Serbia for vacation, "sightseeing" was motivating 63% of tourists, followed by nature (38%), gastronomy (33%), weekend trips (32%), entertainment and festivals (25%), and others. For most foreign tourists, the main source of information about Serbia before the trip was is the Internet (53%)

To conclude, foreign tourists in Serbia mostly come from Russia, Turkey, Bulgaria or Romania. Considering Novi Pazar, foreign tourists are mainly from Turkey and Germany. Other bigger groups are from Bosnia, Macedonia, Montenegro which are considered "domestic" tourists in this research. Most of them are between 25 and 44. They are generally educated and employed. Every third tourist is coming for sightseeing. They are mostly attracted by nature, gastronomy, weekend trips. The internet is the main source of information for more than half of them. As the result, ideal tourism website of Novi Pazar must be adopted to ex-Yugoslavian tourists. Furthermore, it should be adopted and translated Turkish and German language. It should be adopted to relatively young travellers, with modern design. It should have information about, sightseeing points, natural beauties, tips about food and tricks how to spend one, two or three nights in the city.

3. Cultural analysis

Culture dictates the behaviour of tourists as well as their expectations and needs. Therefore, cultural analysis sets important standards. In order to conduct cultural analysis this paper relies on Hofstede’s cultural taxonomies (Hofstede 1991,2011) as well as his resources from his Hofstede Insights website(Insights, 2023a, 2023b). The taxonomies illustrate certain behaviour patterns through five categories as Lalita and Ajay (2011) explain:

- Power Distance

Table 1. Power distance website content variables

High power distance tourists	Low power distance tourists
Formal and respectful interactions	Informal and egalitarian interactions
Clear recommendations for attractions	Options for attractions
Fabricated itineraries	Itineraries with a lot of options
Sites about authority figures, historical hierarchies	Sites about common people

Power distance represents the extent to which the less powerful members of institutions and organizations accept that power is distributed unequally. Tourists from countries with high power distance might expect more formal and respectful interactions with service providers, such as hotel staff or tour guides. Clear hierarchies and deference to authority figures may be important. In contrast, in countries with low power distance, tourists might expect more informal and egalitarian interactions. High power distance cultures may lead to tourists relying more on the recommendations and decisions of tour guides, travel agents, or local experts. In low power distance cultures, tourists may feel more empowered to make independent decisions about their travel plans. High power distance cultures, attractions and historical sites might be presented with a strong emphasis on authority figures, historical hierarchies, and traditional power structures. In low power distance cultures, attractions might focus more on egalitarian perspectives and the contributions of ordinary people. Tour guides' communication styles and the information they prioritize may vary based on the power distance of the tourists they are guiding. Guides catering to tourists from high power distance cultures might use more formal language and focus on authority figures, while guides for tourists from low power distance cultures might adopt a more casual approach.

- Uncertainty Avoidance

Table 2. Uncertainty avoidance website content variables

High uncertainty avoidance	Low uncertainty avoidance
Well-structured itinerary	Itinerary with a lot of optional elements
Clear guidance without variations	Guidance opens to alternatives

Uncertainty avoidance features for tourists are presented in the Table 2.

Uncertainty avoidance represents the extent to which people feel threatened by ambiguous situations, and have created beliefs and institutions that try to avoid in such situations. Tourists from cultures with high uncertainty avoidance may prefer well-structured and meticulously planned trips. They might be more likely to rely on travel agencies, guided tours, and pre-arranged itineraries to ensure a sense of security and minimize unexpected situations. Tourists from cultures with low uncertainty avoidance might be more comfortable with spontaneous travel decisions. They may embrace uncertainty and be open to exploring new and unplanned experiences during their trip. Tourists from cultures with high uncertainty avoidance may react strongly to unexpected changes or disruptions in their travel plans. They might prefer destinations and services that provide clear guidelines and contingency plans for unexpected situations. Tourists from cultures with low uncertainty avoidance may be more adaptable and less distressed by unexpected changes. They might be more open to alternative solutions and improvisation.

– Individualism versus Collectivism

Table 3. Individualism website content variables

Individualistic	Collectivistic
Individual tourist, who come alone or in small groups	Come in groups
Personal guides	Group guidance
Flexible schedules	Structured itineraries
Personal experience, freedom and self-expression	Well-structured and fixed schedules
	Social bonding, group experience

This category represents a situation in which people are supposed to look after themselves and their immediate family only (Individualism). A situation in which people belong to in-group or collectivises, which are supposed to look after them, in exchange for loyalty (Collectivism).

Tourists from cultures with high individualism might seek unique and personalized experiences. They may prefer self-guided tours, individual exploration, and activities that cater to their specific interests. These tourists are likely to prioritize their own preferences and desires over group consensus. Tourists from cultures with low individualism may prioritize group activities and guided tours. They might place greater emphasis on shared experiences and enjoy group-oriented activities that foster social cohesion.

Tourists from individualistic cultures may design their itineraries based on personal interests and desires. They may opt for flexible schedules and the freedom to make spontaneous choices during their trip. Collectivistic tourists might prefer pre-organized tours and structured itineraries that allow them to experience destinations as a group and share the experience with others. Marketing campaigns targeting individualistic tourists could focus on personalized experiences, freedom, and self-expression. Emphasizing the uniqueness of a destination and how it caters to individual interests can be effective. Marketing efforts for collectivistic tourists might highlight group experiences, social bonding, and opportunities to connect with other travellers.

– Masculinity versus Femininity:

The elements are summed in the Table 4.

Table 4. Masculine and Feminine website content variables

Masculine	Feminine
Adrenaline pumping, extreme experience	Relaxation, wellness, well-being
Challenges, achievement	Quality of life

Masculinity versus Femininity represents a situation in which the dominant values of society are success, money, and things (Masculinity). A situation in which the dominant values of a society are caring for others and quality of life (Femininity). Tourists from cultures with high masculinity values might seek adrenaline-pumping and competitive activities such as adventure sports, extreme outdoor experiences, and challenging physical pursuits.

Tourists from cultures with high femininity values might prioritize relaxation, wellness, and activities that promote emotional well-being, such as spa retreats, cultural experiences, and nature appreciation. Marketing efforts targeting tourists from cultures with high masculinity might focus on challenges, achievements, and opportunities for personal growth. Marketing efforts targeting tourists from cultures with high femininity might highlight relaxation, emotional well-being, and the quality of life that the destination offers.

– Long term orientation

Table 5. Long term orientation website content variables

Long term oriented	Short term oriented
Trip planned in advance	Spontaneously planned trip
Meaningful and transformative experience	Immediate gratification
Cultural immersion, historical exploration	Entertainment, relaxation, immediate enjoyment

This dimension measures a society's orientation towards the future, emphasizing values such as perseverance, thrift, and a willingness to delay gratification for long-term goals. Tourists from cultures with high LTO may plan their trips well in advance, considering long-term goals and seeking meaningful and transformative experiences. They might be more willing to invest time and effort in researching destinations and planning detailed itineraries. Tourists from cultures with low LTO may be more spontaneous in their travel decisions, focusing on immediate gratification and enjoying the present moment. They might be more open to last-minute trips and flexible itineraries. Tourists with a high LTO might be interested in cultural immersion, historical exploration, and activities that offer opportunities for personal growth and self-discovery over the long term. Tourists with a low LTO might prioritize entertainment, relaxation, and activities that

provide immediate enjoyment and instant gratification. Tourists with a high LTO may be more interested in building long-term relationships with locals and fellow travellers, seeking meaningful connections and lasting friendships. Tourists with a low LTO might focus more on individual experiences and may be less inclined to invest time in forming deep relationships during their short stay.

– Indulgence versus Restraint

Table 6. Indulgence website content variables

High indulgence	Low indulgence
Sensory pleasure, entertainment	Self-discipline, self-control
Gourmet dining, nightlife	Nature focused, wellness retreat
Leisure, enjoyment, luxury experience	Cultural authority, tranquillity, self-improvement

This dimension explores the extent to which a society allows individuals to satisfy their natural human desires and enjoy life without guilt or social restraint. It is often linked to the control of gratification and how societies approach pleasure and self-indulgence. Tourists from high indulgence countries are more likely to pursue leisure activities, entertainment, and self-expression without strict societal norms inhibiting them. Tourists from low indulgence cultures may feel more constrained in their pursuit of personal enjoyment and may prioritize discipline, self-control, and adherence to social norms. A tourist content creator should emphasize enjoyment in images, texts or video material such as food, parties and similar. As for the other group an adaptation expert should abstain from such photos.

Tourists from cultures with high indulgence values might seek experiences that provide sensory pleasure, entertainment, and opportunities for leisure and enjoyment, such as gourmet dining, nightlife, and luxury spa treatments. Tourists from cultures with low indulgence values might prioritize activities that align with self-discipline and self-control, such as wellness retreats, nature-focused experiences, and educational trips. Marketing efforts targeting tourists from high indulgence cultures might highlight opportunities for leisure, enjoyment, and luxury experiences. Marketing efforts targeting tourists from low indulgence cultures might emphasize cultural authenticity, tranquillity, and activities that promote self-improvement.

It's important to note that these dimensions are not judgments of superiority or inferiority but rather tools for understanding and comparing cultural differences. They can help individuals and organizations gain insights into how different societies approach various aspects of life, such as time orientation and attitudes towards pleasure and restraint. It's also worth mentioning that Hofstede's cultural dimensions are based on extensive research and have been widely used in cross-cultural studies and international business contexts.

3.1. Cultural profile – Domestic group

In this section the paper represents cultural features of the tourists who visit Novi Pazar the most. Domestic tourists are represented in the first part, figures of foreignt tourists follow them. It will show how the tourits groups are similar or dissimilar and how the content should be adopted.

Figure 1. Cultural taxonomy of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia

Source: Insights, 2023

As it can be seen the tourists from all four countries are culturally very similar in all categories except in Indulgence categories. High power distance cultures may emphasize the role of hosts as providers of service, and tourists may expect a high level of attention and assistance. In low power distance cultures, interactions between hosts and tourists might be more relaxed and focused on equality. High power distance cultures may lead to tourists relying more on the recommendations and decisions of tour guides, travel agents, or local experts. For high power distance cultures, attractions and historical sites might be presented with a strong emphasis on authority figures, historical hierarchies, and traditional power structures. Guides catering to tourists from high power distance cultures might use more formal language and focus on authority figures.

Table 7. Domestic tourist group cultural features

Formal and respectful interactions
Clear recommendations for attractions
Fabricated itineraries
Sites about authority figures, historical hierarchies
Come in groups
Group guidance
Structured itineraries
Well-structured and fixed schedules
Social bonding, group experience
Relaxation, wellness, well-being
Quality of life
Well-structured itinerary
Clear guidance without variations
Trip planned in advance
Meaningful and transformative experience
Cultural immersion, historical exploration
Self-discipline, self-control
Nature focused, wellness retreat
Cultural authority, tranquility, self-improvement

3.2 Cultural profile – Foreign group

Figure 2. Country comparison tool: Germany, Turkey

Source: Insights, 2023b

As it can be observed Turkish and German cultural group differ significantly in all categories. Therefore, the content creator should create two separate localizations. If one compares Turkish results with domestic tourist cultural groups, one will observe many similarities. Therefore, there should be a Turkish version of domestic group adapted content. German tourist group should have its own version with different content.

German content should be oriented towards the elements in the following table 8:

Table 8. German tourist group cultural features

Informal and egalitarian interactions
 Options for attractions
 Itineraries with a lot of options
 Sites about common people
 Individual tourist, who come alone or in small groups
 Personal guides
 Flexible schedules
 Personal experience, freedom and self-expression
 Adrenaline pumping, extreme experience
 Challenges, achievement
 Trip planned in advance
 Meaningful and transformative experience
 Cultural immersion, historical exploration
 Self-discipline, self-control
 Nature focused, wellness retreat
 Cultural authority, tranquillity, self-improvement
 Well-structured itinerary
 Clear guidance without variations

4. Website analysis

As the website is too large the analysis will be conducted on a representative part of the website. That representative part is Tours section. The section is translated and adopted in three languages: Bosnian, English and German. There are three tours: old town tour, UNESCO sites tour and the Uvac river meanders tours. The images of the parts as well as the translation of the content is represented in the annex of this document. The analysis is conducted on content level. The existing textual content is analysed though the cultural elements of domestic and foreign group delivered in previous sections of the paper. In the end there is a conclusion where the result of the assessment is represented with notes for further development.

Bosnian language version analysis

Good sides	Bad sides
The language is understandable to all groups.	
Formal interactions	
Sites about authority figures, historical hierarchies There is an adaptation of Unesco tour to Bosnian language – “Footsteps on Nemanjic Dynasty”. That adaptation targets this element of historical figures important for the history of the Balkan region.	Social bonding, group experience There are no options for social bonding such as team activities and games. There are rarely any indications of collective experience.
Fabricated itineraries All the itineraries are premade. So, the tourist feels safe and under control. There are strict timings and description of activities.	Relaxation, wellness, well-being There are a lot of descriptions of nature but the translator and writer rarely mention how a person can relax. There are no mentioned relaxation activities as massages or yoga which are very attractive to the tourists.
Cultural immersion, historical exploration This element is especially recognizable in the “Old town tour”. Even the title is in Bosnian - <i>carsija</i> which is an old Turkish word for town centre. There is a direct reference to cultural immersion calling the tourists to visit Bosniak room, culture and try traditional dishes.	Cultural authority, tranquillity, self-improvement There are no direct references to self-improvement and tranquillity. A tourist can guess but the writer should make clear references to how the tour can improve oneself.
Nature focused, wellness retreat This element is clearly present in the tour “Meanders of the Uvac river”. The content writer lures and calls the tourists to enjoy the view, smell and wonders of nature.	

The content for domestic tourists is well adapted. There are a lot of elements that answer cultural needs of that group. It is also positive that all the domestic tourist can understand the language of the webpage. The itinerary and the choice of words and phrases target domestic tourists in a favourable way. On the other hand, as those tourists come in small or big groups there should be mentions of activities and games that focus on collaboration. There also should be more and direct connotations of relaxation and nature. The website is not translated to Turkish language although the Turks are frequent tourists to the city. The content for this cultural group can be the same as for domestic tourists as they share similar features.

German language version

Good sides	Bad sides
	Informal and egalitarian interactions The tone of the language is quite formal. There are no jokes or other tourist comments.
	Options for attractions or activities Although the website has a whole page of attractions and activities. Those website elements and texts are not integrated into tours. There should be optional parts such as you can also do: hiking, climbing, paragliding in tour sections.
Personal guides There is a clear information about personal guides with name and surname as well as a mobile phone.	Sites about common people, cultural immersion There is rarely any information about common people or sites. The personal touch and the contact with the locals are very important to foreign tourist. The translator should add those options such as to meet a villager, a priest or imam from the mosque.
Nature focused, wellness retreat There are clear references for nature focused experience especially in Uvac meanders tour and UNESCO tour. However, one should add options for hiking.	Personal experience, freedom and self-expression There are no options for foreign tourists to express themselves. There is no option to leave a comment on the page. Moreover, there is no place for a tourist to make one's impression about the place such as a vlog, blog. That option should be added.
	Adrenaline pumping, extreme experience Although there is an activity of paragliding and quad driving as well as climbing, the translator and writer did not put it in this section as optional activities.

Considering the German version, it is evident that the translator hasn't paid attention to the cultural features of this group. The tone of the language can be more colloquial. There are no optional activities or attractions. German tourists want freedom of expression and the contact with the locals, which is not presented in the tours.

5. Conclusion

The promotional tourist website novipazar.travel is well adopted to domestic tourist as the content correlates with the cultural features of the groups. It is also statistically well adapted as the most frequent tourist are tourist from domestic group of countries: Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia and Montenegro. The localized content relates well to the cultural and statistical features of domestic tourists. Pull-effect of the destination image is successfully made though linguistic elements of official language, historical data on important persons and similar. However, the adaptation for foreign group of tourists is not as good as the first adaptation for domestic group. Firstly, there is no Turkish language version of the website. Secondly, the adaptation poorly correlates with the cultural feature of German tourists. Although there is a German version of the website the content is not adopted to this group which favours freedom of expression, contact with nature and local as well as self-development and adrenaline activities. The localization expert should pay more attention to the development of German content. The Turkish version should be very similar almost an equal version as for the domestic tourists.

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Appendix

Statistical data of tourists visits in 2022 to Novi Pazar provided by Tourist Organization of Novi Pazar

Novi Pazar		2022
Country	Incomings	Sleepovers
All together	20692	40042
Domestic tourists	10782	21383
Foreign tourists all together	9910	18659
Albania	117	244
Australia	27	68
Austria	219	496
Belgium	60	157
Belarus	5	9
Bosnia and Herzegovina	4104	5522
Brazil	10	20
Bulgaria	179	227
Great Britain	54	79
Greece	30	52
Denmark	16	83
Egypt	17	27
Israel	18	21
India	66	92
Iran	15	24
Ireland	10	17
Iceland	3	50
Italy	137	262
Japan	17	23
South Africa	2	2
Canada	29	65
China and Hong Kong	43	82
Luxemburg	64	140
Hungary	125	144
Germany	695	2017
New Zealand	1	1
Norway	27	49
Other non-European countries	245	842
Other European countries	15	28
Poland	83	145
Portugal	5	6
Republic of Korea	2	2
Romania	235	253
Russian Federation	98	163
North Macedonia	353	532
United States of Amerika	128	285
Slovakia	21	64
Slovenia	136	196
Turkey	946	3066
United Arab Emirates	54	103
Ukraine	83	144
Finland	15	26
France	121	263
Netherlands	92	235
Croatia	140	327
Montenegro	665	1212
Czech Republic	46	71
Switzerland and Lichtenstein	90	246
Sweden	123	304
Spain	124	173

Novipazar.travel website, Tours category content in different languages

Bosnian language version

Ture

Vožnja čamcem Molitva vidikovac Prevoz

Meadrima Uvca

⌚ 5h
✓ Već od 150eu po osobi

Gradska tvrđava Kula Motrilja Altun Alem dzamija
Hamam

Čaršijska tura

⌚ 1h
✓ Već od 40 po osobi

Manastir Sopoćani Manastir Đurđevi Stupovi
Petrova crkva

Stopama Nemanjića

⌚ 3h
✓ Već od 60 po osobi

Meadrima Uvca

Jedno od najposećenijih mesta u Srbiji

🕒 5h

Vožnja čamcem

Molitva vidikovac

Prevoz

Malo je reći da su prirodne lepote ovog dela Srbije neverovatne. Meandri reke Uvca su jedno od mesta u Srbiji koje morate posetiti. Za ovu turu postoji ogromno interesovanje, ne samo domaćih već i stranih turista.

Ovo putovanje počinje prolaskom kroz najlepše delove okoline Novog Pazara. Radi se o visoravni Pešter. Osećaćete se kao da niste u Srbiji već u Mongoliji ili Kanadi. Nećete moći da prestanete da uživate u pejzažima Pešteri.

Ponesite duksericu, udobnu obuću za pešačenje, vodu i rezervnu odeću.

Polazimo iz Novog Pazara ujutru. Nakon 40 minuta nezaboravne vožnje pravimo pauzu u hotelu Borovi u Sjenici gde nas dočekuje lokalni vodič koji organizuje brodove.

Vreme je za nezaboravnu avanturu vode, vazduha i leda!

Idemo do mesta za ukrcajanje u brodove i polazimo. Osetićete neverovatan spoj mirisa trave, šume i vetra koji donosi svežinu sa obližnjih planina koji se mešaju sa vlagom i notama vode. Pogledaj gore beskraino nebo koje presecaju beloglavi supovi, čija dužina krila prelazi polovinu broda kojim se vozite. Pogledajte levo i desno, videćete stene na kojima se ove veličanstvene ptice neretko odmaraju. Lako je pomisliti da je takav prizor običan, ali nije. To su prizori kojima se hvale veliki svetski putnici i velike države u svetu. Ovog puta vi ste putnik koji shvata veličinu i lepotu Srbije.

Zaustavljamo se i uzimamo opremu za ulazak u pećinu. Ne zaboravite da ponesete duksericu ili jaknu jer je temperatura u pećini oko 15 stepeni, bez obzira na temperaturu vani. Čim joj se približite osetićete hladni dah zemlje u čuđe mistične hodnike ulazimo. Pećina se sa pravom zove Ledena pećina zbog pećinskog nakita koje se u njoj nalazi, a izgleda kao okamenjeni led. Pomislite da ulazite u neko skriveno podzemno carstvo patuljaka kada budete prolazili kroz pećinske hodnike i dvorane.

Pri izlasku će vas dočekati nasmejano lice čamdžije koji će vas vratiti na mesto polaska.

Postoji i opcija za one vrednije i fizički spremnije za pešačenje do vidikovcima Molitva sa kojeg se pruža pogled na meandre koji će vam večno ostati u srcima. Uspon je strm tako da ga ne savetujemo starijima i onima koji imaju srčanih problema. Savetujemo da ponesete i rezervnu odeću, jer će te sigurno oznojiti a na vidikovcu uvek duva vetar.

Nakon toga preporučujemo ručak u hotelu Borovi.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

> Cena za grupe: 150eu€

> Cena za individualce: 50€

Kontakt info

+381649746676

eccodoo@gmail.com

www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

> Cena za grupe: 150eu€

> Cena za individualce: 50€

Kontakt info

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Podeli

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 40€
- > Cena za individualce: 40€

Kontakt info

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- www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Čaršijska tura

Obilazimo najznačajnija mesta u staroj čaršiji

1h

- Gradska tvrđava
- Kula Motrilja
- Altun Alem dzamija
- Hamam

Osetite tragove Istanbula, Bagdada, islama i orijenta u uskim ulicama stare čaršije. Neka vam ljubaznost Novopazaraca izmami osmeh i toplinu u srcu. Posetite gradsku tvrđavu i simbol grada kulu Motrilju. Popijte kafu u hamamu starom skoro šest vekova.

Turisti iz Srbije posebno vole ovu turu jer imaju priliku da uspostave kontakt sa komšijama Bošnjacima. Imaju priliku da posete islamsku bogomolju, bošnjačku sobu i da pitaju sve što žele o bošnjačkoj kulturi i Islamu koja je nažalost pod uticajem lažnih vesti i medija ocrnjena i satanizovana.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 40€
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Kontakt info

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Podeli

Dalje prolazimo kroz trg **Isa-bega Isakovića**, osnivača Novog Pazara pre više od 550 godina. Odatle se pruža neverovatan pogled na **Bedem** – simbol grada odnosno deo tvrđave na kojoj se nalazi gradska biblioteka. Uz priču o istoriji Novog Pazara u Osmanlijskom carstvu ulazimo u **gradski park u tvrđavi**. Videćete **kulu Motrilju** koja motri na grad već više od dva veka. Uz to se ona nalazi na grbu grada Novog Pazara.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 40€
- > Cena za individualce: 40€

Kontakt info

- +381649746676
- eccodoo@gmail.com
- www.ecco.rs

Podeli

[Pošalji upit](#)

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 60€
- > Cena za individualce: 50€

Kontakt info

- ☎ +381649746676
- ✉ eccodoo@gmail.com
- 🌐 www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Stopama Nemanjića

UNESCO: Petrova crkva, Đurđevi Stupovi, Sopoćani

🕒 3h

Manastir Sopoćani

Manastir Đurđevi Stupovi

Petrova crkva

Posvedočite veličanstvenost srpske istorije i kulturnog nasleđa Srbije! Ovo je kolevka gde se Republika Srbija rodila ovde su Nemanjići osnovali srpsku srednjovekovnu državu na čijem osnovu postoji današnja republika. Svi spomenici koji se obilaze u ovoj turi, zbog lepote i istorije, pripadaju svetskoj kulturnoj baštini pod okriljem UNESCO-a. Ljudi iz celog sveta dolaze da posete ove jedinstvene spomenike srpske kulture.

U toku ove ture ćete doživeti spomenike hrišćanske srednjovekovne srpske države (**Petrova crkva**, **manastir Đurđevi stupovi** i **manastir Sopoćani**) koji predstavljaju bisere sažimanja istoka i zapada u arhitekturi i fresko slikarstvu. Zbog te jedinstvene sinteze ove spomenike posećuju ne samo vernici već i zaljubljenici u istoriju, kulturu i umetnost.

Uz pogled koji uzima dah na planine **Goliju**, **Rogoznu**, **Kopaonik** i **Peštersku visoravan** nastavljamo prema manastiru Sopoćani, jednom od najlepših i jedinstvenih manastira u Srbiji.

Prateći dolinu reke Raške po kojoj je Ras dobio ime, susrećemo se sa ostacima grada Trgovišta i utvrđenja Gradine iznad njega. To naselje ima bogatu istoriju jer podaci govore da su je naseljavali Rimljani, a kasnije bilo važno vojno-strateško utvrđenje.

[Pošalji upit](#)

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 60€
- > Cena za individualce: 50€

Kontakt info

- ☎ +381649746676
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- 🌐 www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Manastir Sopoćani je izgradio kralj Uroš u 13. veku. Odmah će vas zapleniti svojom elegantnošću koja krase jedinstvenu rašku školu arhitekture kojoj pripada. Sopoćani su dobili ime po reči sopot što znači izvor. U blizini se nalazi izvor Raške. Sopoćani su sinteza istoka i zapada. Ukoliko bolje pogledate videćete da spolja liči na zapadne katedrale. Unutrašnjost je vizantijska. Uroš je uposlio najbolje slikare koji su svojim slikarskim umećem nagovestili dolazak Renesanse u Evropi. Freska koja pleni nijansama i umetničkim umećem prikazivanja emocija je Uspeće svete Bogorodice. Tu je još i srpska Mona Liza odnosno freska sv. apostola Filipa koja kao i pomenuto delo Da Vinčija prati pogledom onoga ko je posmatra.

Nakon obilaska Sopoćana preporučujemo odmor ili ručak u idiličnom restoranu **Pazarište** gde ćete uz umirujuće zvuke reke Raške i opijajuću pesmu ptica iz obližnje šume uživati u tradicionalnim pazarskim obrocima.

Pre svega tu je **Petrova crkva**. Na izgled skroman hram, ali sa ogromnim istorijskim i kulturološkim nasledem. Ova crkva je mesto gde je Stefan Nemanja kršten, oženjen i gde je on predao vlast svom sinu prvom srpskom kralju. U blizini Novog Pazara je boravio i Rastko Nemanjić – Sveti Sava. Crkva Svetog Petra i Pavla je jedna od najstarijih crkvi na Balkanu. Prema zvaničnim podacima datira iz 13. veka. Prema nezvaničnim podacima Petrova crkva je nastala puno pre. Jedna priča kaže da je crkvu osnovao Tit učenik Svetog Pavla i da je on u čast svog učitelja nazvao po njemu.

Petrova crkva je jedan od najstarijih verskih objekata na Balkanu. Ispod ove crkve je pre bila rimski hram. Delove tog hrama možete i danas naći u crkvi, pitajte vodiča.

Ispod hrama je nekada bila humka ili grobnica. U njoj je pronađen nakit iz 5. veka pre nove ere koji se čuva u Beogradu tzv. **Novopazarski nalaz**. To čini ovaj skromni spomenik starim više od dve i po hiljade godina.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 60€
- > Cena za individualce: 50€

Kontakt info

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Podeli

Pošalji upit

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- > Cena za individualce: 50€

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Podeli

Dalje nastavljamo sa manastirom **Durđevi stupovi** koji je star više od 800 godina. Osnovao ga je Stefan Nemanja, rodonačelnik dinastije Nemanjića uz to i države Srbije. Svojom jedinstvenom arhitekturom i geografskim položajem na vrhu brda nadvisuje celu dolinu i pleni pažnju posmatrača. Pored crkve Svetog Đorda, posetićemo i Dragutinovu kapelu. U njoj je oslikan državni sabor u Rasu. U njemu se takođe nalazi i oslikana loza Nemanjića.

Ukoliko želite možemo otići i do manastira **Studenica**. On se nalazi na jedan sat vožnje od Novog Pazara. Manastir je poznat kao jedan od najlepših, a možda i najbolji manastir Nemanjića poznat o freskopisu i prelepoj plavoj boji.

Iz grada se uskim ulicama probijamo do **Altun-alem džamije**. Tu ćete čuti dirljivu priču o Altuni, zanosnoj čerci bega, čiji je život usko povezan sa ovom džamijom. Imaćete priliku da uđete u džamiju, gde će vam vodič pričati o Islamu.

Nakon dodira istoka idemo dalje prema **hamamu** ili **kupatilu** iz šesnaestog veka koji čeka restauraciju. Dok se to ne izvrši u hamamu možete popiti kafu u atmosferi kao nigde u svetu.

Nakon predaha idemo u **gradski muzej** gde ćete imati priliku da zavirite u tradicionalne postavke soba – bošnjačke i srpske. Pri tome ćete posvedočiti razlikama i sličnosti ovih dveju tradicija.

+381649746676

eccodoo@gmail.com

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Podeli

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

> Cena za grupe: 40€

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Kontakt info

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Podeli

English language version

Ture

Boat ride Molitva Sightseeing point Drive to Sjenica

Meanders of Heaven – Uvac

5h

✓ Već od 150eu po osobi

Sopoćani St. Peter's Church Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery Sopoćani Monastery

UNESCO Monastery Tour

3h

✓ Već od 60 po osobi

City Fortress Watch Tower Altun Alem Mosque Old Turkish Bath

Oriental Old Town Tour

1h

✓ Već od 40 po osobi

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 150eu€
- > Cena za individualce: 70eu€

Kontakt info

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Podeli

Meanders of Heaven – Uvac

One of the most famous sights in the Balkan and Serbia.

🕒 5h

- Boat ride
- Molitva Sightseeing point
- Drive to Sjenica

It is an understatement to say that the natural beauty of this part of Serbia is incredible. The meanders of the Uvac River are one of the places in Serbia that you must visit. There is a huge interest in this tour, not only from domestic but also from foreign tourists.

This journey begins with passing through the most beautiful parts of the surroundings of Novi Pazar. It is about the Pešter plateau. You will feel as if you are not in Serbia but in Mongolia or Canada. You will not be able to stop enjoying the landscapes of the Caves.

Bring a hoodie, comfortable walking shoes, water and spare clothes.

We leave Novi Pazar in the morning. After 40 minutes of unforgettable driving, we take a break at the Borovi hotel in Sjenica, where we are greeted by a local guide who organizes the boats.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 150eu€
- > Cena za individualce: 70eu€

Kontakt info

- +381649746676
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- www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 60€
- > Cena za individualce: 50€

Kontakt info

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Podeli

UNESCO Monastery Tour

UNESCO sites: St. Peter's Church, Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery, Sopoćani Monastery

3h

- Sopoćani
- St. Peter's Church
- Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery
- Sopoćani Monastery

All monuments that are visited in this tour, due to their beauty and history, belong to the world cultural heritage under the auspices of UNESCO. People from all over the world come to visit these unique monuments of Serbian culture.

During this tour, you will experience the monuments of the Christian medieval Serbian state (Peter's Church, Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery and Sopoćani Monastery), which represent the pearls of the fusion of East and West in architecture and fresco painting. Due to this unique synthesis, these monuments are visited not only by believers but also by lovers of history, culture and art.

With a breath-taking view of the mountains Golija, Rogozna, Kopaonik and the Pešter plateau, we continue towards the Sopoćani monastery, one of the most beautiful and unique monasteries in Serbia.

Following the valley of the Raška River, after which Ras got its name, we come across the remains of the town of Trgoviste and the fortress of Gradina above it. That settlement has a rich history because the data shows that it was inhabited by the Romans, and later it was an important military-strategic fortification.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 60€
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Podeli

The Sopoćani Monastery was built by King Uroš in the 13th century. It will immediately captivate you with its elegance, which adorns the unique Raška school of architecture to which it belongs. The people of Sopot got their name from the word sopot, which means source. The Raška spring is located nearby. Sopoćani are a synthesis of East and West. If you look closely, you will see that it looks like western cathedrals from the outside. The interior is Byzantine. Uroš employed the best painters who, with their painting skills, hinted at the arrival of the Renaissance in Europe. A fresco that captivates with nuances and the artistic skill of depicting emotions is the Succession of the Holy Virgin. There is also the Serbian Mona Lisa, i.e. the fresco of St. of the Apostle Philip, which, like the aforementioned work by Da Vinci, follows the beholder's gaze.

After visiting Sopoćan, we recommend a rest or lunch at the idyllic restaurant Pazariste, where you will enjoy traditional Pazar meals with the soothing sounds of the Raška river and the intoxicating song of birds from the nearby forest.

First of all, there is St. Peter's church. A seemingly modest temple, but with a huge historical and cultural heritage. This church is the place where Stefan Nemanja was baptized, married, and where he handed over power to his son, the first Serbian king. Rastko Nemanjić – Sveti Sava also lived near Novi Pazar. The Church of Saints Peter and Paul is one of the oldest churches in the Balkans. According to official data, it dates back to the 13th century. According to unofficial data, Peter's church was built much earlier. One story says that the church was founded by Titus, a disciple of St. Paul, and that he named it after him in honor of his teacher.

Peter's Church is one of the oldest religious buildings in the Balkans. Below this church was a Roman temple. You can still find parts of that temple in the church today, ask the guide.

There used to be a mound or tomb under the temple. Jewelry from the 5th century BC was found in it, which is kept in Belegrade History Museum. This makes this modest monument more than two and a half thousand years old.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

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Podeli

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Podeli

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

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Kontakt info

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www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Oriental Old Town Tour

Experiencing the oriental spirit of the town

1h

- City Fortress
- Watch Tower
- Altun Alem Mosque
- Old Turkish Bath

Feel the traces of Istanbul, Baghdad, Islam and the Orient in the narrow streets of the old bazaar. May the kindness of the people of Novopazar make you smile and warm your heart. Visit the city fortress and the symbol of the city, the Motrilja Watch tower. Drink a coffee in a hammam that is almost six centuries old.

Pošalji upit

Tourists from all over the world especially like this tour because they have the opportunity to establish contact with unique Islamic heritage in Europe. They have the opportunity to visit the Islamic place of worship, the Bosniak room and to ask everything they want about Bosniak culture and Islam, which is unfortunately denigrated and demonized under the influence of fake news and media.

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 40€
- > Cena za individualce: 40€

Kontakt info

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www.ecco.rs

Podeli

*We meet at the **Sebilj** or fountain in the famous oriental edition. Water occupies a very important place in Islam as in Novi Pazar, it symbolizes the change and cleaning – as may you feel at the end of the tour.*

*We continue with the tour of **Amir-aga's han**. You will see what a medieval Turkish hostel for merchants looks like.*

*Further on, we pass through the square of **Isa-bey Isaković**, the founder of Novi Pazar more than 550 years ago. From there, there is an incredible view of the **Wall** – the symbol of the city, i.e. part of the fortress where the city library is located. With a story about the history of Novi Pazar in the Ottoman Empire, we enter the city park in the fortress. You will see the **Motrilja Watch tower**, which has been watching over the city for more than two centuries. In addition, it is found on the coat of arms of the city of Novi Pazar.*

*From the city, we make our way through the narrow streets to the **Altun-alem mosque**. There you will hear the touching story of **Altuna**, the ravishing daughter of the bey, whose life is closely connected with this mosque. You will have the opportunity to enter the mosque, where the guide will tell you about Islam. After touching the east, we continue towards the **sixteenth-century hammam**, or bathhouse, which is awaiting restoration. Until that is done in the hammam you can drink coffee in an atmosphere like nowhere else in the world.*

*After a break, we will go to the **city museum**, where you will have the opportunity to take a look at the traditional settings of the rooms – **Bosniak** and **Serbian**. In doing so, you will witness the differences and similarities of these two traditions.*

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

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Podeli

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Podeli

German language version

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

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Kontakt info

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Podeli

Oriental Old Town Tour

Experiencing the oriental spirit of the town

1h

- City Fortress
- Watch Tower
- Altun Alem Mosque
- Old Turkish Bath

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Podeli

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Pošalji upit

We continue with the tour of **Amir-aga's han**. You will see what a medieval Turkish hostel for merchants looks like.

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Podeli

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German Language content

Ture

- die Stadtburg
- Motrilja Turm
- Altun Alem Moschee
- Altes Türkisches Hammam

Orient Altstadt Tour

- 🕒 1h
- ✓ Već od 40 po osobi

- St. Peter's Kirche
- Đurđevi Stupovi Kloster
- Sopoćani Kloster

UNESCO Tour

- 🕒 3h
- ✓ Već od 60 po osobi

- Boat drive
- Motrija Sightseeing Point
- Drive to Sjenica

Wunder der Natur

- 🕒 5h
- ✓ Već od 150€ po osobi

Orient Altstadt Tour

Das Erleben des orientalischen Geistes der Stadt.

🕒 1h

die Stadtburg Motrija Turm Altun Alem Moschee Alles Türkisches Hammam

Fühlen Sie die Spuren von Istanbul, Bagdad, Islam und dem Orient in den engen Gassen des alten Basars. Möge die Freundlichkeit der Menschen von Novopazar Sie zum Lächeln bringen und Ihr Herz erwärmen. Besuchen Sie die Stadtburg und das Wahrzeichen der Stadt, den Motrija Wachturm. Trinken Sie einen Kaffee in einem Hamam, das fast sechs Jahrhunderte alt ist.

Touristen aus aller Welt schätzen diese Tour besonders, weil sie die Möglichkeit haben, Kontakt mit dem einzigartigen islamischen Erbe in Europa aufzunehmen. Sie haben die Gelegenheit, den islamischen Gebetsraum, den Bosniakenraum, zu besuchen und alles zu fragen, was sie über die bosniakische Kultur und den Islam wissen möchten, der leider unter dem Einfluss von Fake News und Medien verunglimpft und dämonisiert wird.

Wir treffen uns am *Sebilj oder Brunnen* in der berühmten orientalischen Ausgabe. Wasser nimmt im Islam und in Novi Pazar einen sehr wichtigen Platz ein. Es symbolisiert Veränderung und Reinigung – so können Sie sich am Ende der Tour fühlen.

Wir setzen die Tour mit dem *Amir-Agas Han* fort. Dort werden Sie sehen, wie ein mittelalterliches türkisches Gasthaus für Händler aussieht.

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

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www.ecco.rs

Podeli

Weiter geht es durch den Platz von Isa-Bey Isaković, dem Gründer von Novi Pazar vor mehr als 550 Jahren. Von dort aus haben Sie einen unglaublichen Blick auf die Stadtmauer – das Symbol der Stadt bzw. den Teil der Burg, in dem sich die Stadtbibliothek befindet. Mit einer Geschichte über die Geschichte von Novi Pazar im Osmanischen Reich betreten wir den Stadtpark in der Burg. Dort werden Sie den Motrija Wachturm sehen, der seit mehr als zwei Jahrhunderten über die Stadt wacht. Außerdem ist er auf dem Stadtwappen von Novi Pazar zu finden.

Von der Stadt aus machen wir uns auf den Weg durch die engen Gassen zur Altun-Alem-Moschee. Dort hören Sie die berührende Geschichte von Altuna, der bezaubernden Tochter des Beys, deren Leben eng mit dieser Moschee verbunden ist. Sie haben die Gelegenheit, die Moschee zu betreten, wo der Reiseführer Ihnen über den Islam erzählen wird.

Nachdem wir den Osten berührt haben, setzen wir unseren Weg fort in Richtung des Hammams aus dem 16. Jahrhundert, das auf seine Restaurierung wartet. Bis dahin können Sie in einer Atmosphäre, wie es sie sonst nirgendwo auf der Welt gibt, Kaffee trinken.

Nach einer Pause werden wir zum Stadtmuseum gehen, wo Sie die Gelegenheit haben, einen Blick auf die traditionellen Einrichtungen der Zimmer – Bosniakisch und Serbisch – zu werfen. Dabei werden Sie die Unterschiede und Ähnlichkeiten dieser beiden Traditionen erleben.

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 40€
- > Cena za individualce: 40€

Kontakt info

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Podeli

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Podeli

Pošalji upit

Cenovnik

- > Cena za grupe: 60€
- > Cena za individualce: 50€

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UNESCO Tour

UNESCO-Stätten: Kirche St. Peter, Kloster Đurđevi Stupovi, Kloster Sopoćani

🕒 3h

- St. Peter's Kirche
- Đurđevi Stupovi Kloster
- Sopoćani Kloster

Alle Monumente, die während dieser Tour besucht werden, gehören aufgrund ihrer Schönheit und Geschichte zum Weltkulturerbe unter der Schirmherrschaft der UNESCO. Menschen aus der ganzen Welt kommen, um diese einzigartigen Denkmäler der serbischen Kultur zu besuchen.

Während dieser Tour werden Sie die Denkmäler des christlichen mittelalterlichen serbischen Staates (Peterkirche, Kloster Đurđevi Stupovi und Kloster Sopoćani) erleben, die die Perlen der Fusion von Ost und West in Architektur und Freskenmalerei darstellen. Aufgrund dieser einzigartigen Synthese werden diese Denkmäler nicht nur von Gläubigen, sondern auch von Liebhabern von Geschichte, Kultur und Kunst besucht.

Mit einer atemberaubenden Aussicht auf die Berge Golija, Rogozna, Kopaonik und das Pešter-Plateau setzen wir unseren Weg zum Kloster Sopoćani fort, einem der schönsten und einzigartigsten Klöster Serbiens.

Wir folgen dem Tal des Raška-Flusses, nach dem Ras seinen Namen hat, und stoßen auf die Überreste der Stadt Trgoviste und die Festung Gradina darüber. Diese Siedlung hat eine reiche Geschichte, denn die Daten zeigen, dass sie von den Römern bewohnt wurde und später eine wichtige militärisch-strategische Befestigung war.

Pošalji upit

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Podeli

Das Kloster Sopoćani wurde im 13. Jahrhundert von König Uroš erbaut. Es wird Sie sofort mit seiner Eleganz begeistern, die zur einzigartigen Raška-Schule der Architektur gehört. Die Menschen von Sopot haben ihren Namen von dem Wort Sopot, was Quelle bedeutet. Die Raška-Quelle befindet sich in der Nähe. Sopoćani sind eine Synthese aus Ost und West. Wenn Sie genau hinsehen, werden Sie feststellen, dass es von außen wie westliche Kathedralen aussieht. Das Innere ist byzantinisch. Uroš beschäftigte die besten Maler, die mit ihren Malereikünsten auf die Ankunft der Renaissance in Europa hinwiesen.

Ein Fresko, das mit Nuancen und der künstlerischen Fähigkeit zur Darstellung von Emotionen begeistert, ist die Nachfolge der Heiligen Jungfrau. Es gibt auch die serbische Mona Lisa, das Fresko des Heiligen Apostels Philip, das wie das zuvor genannte Werk von Da Vinci den Blick des Betrachters folgt. Nach dem Besuch von Sopoćan empfehlen wir Ihnen eine Ruhepause oder ein Mittagessen im idyllischen Restaurant Paziarište, wo Sie traditionelle Pazar-Gerichte bei den beruhigenden Klängen des Raška-Flusses und dem betörenden Gesang von Vögeln aus dem nahe gelegenen Wald genießen können.

Zunächst besuchen wir die Kirche des Heiligen Petrus. Eine scheinbar bescheidene Kirche, aber mit einem riesigen historischen und kulturellen Erbe. Diese Kirche ist der Ort, an dem Stefan Nemanja getauft wurde, geheiratet hat und wo er die Macht an seinen Sohn, den ersten serbischen König, übergab. Rastko Nemanjić – Sveti Sava lebte ebenfalls in der Nähe von Novi Pazar. Die Kirche der Heiligen Peter und Paulus ist eine der ältesten Kirchen auf dem Balkan. Offiziellen Daten zufolge stammt sie aus dem 13. Jahrhundert. Nach inoffiziellen Daten wurde die Kirche jedoch viel früher erbaut. Eine Geschichte besagt, dass die Kirche von Titus, einem Schüler des St. Paulus, gegründet wurde und dass er sie zu Ehren seines Lehrers nach ihm benannte.

Die Kirche des Heiligen Petrus ist eines der ältesten religiösen Gebäude auf dem Balkan. Unterhalb dieser Kirche befand sich ein römisches Tempelgebäude. Teile dieses Tempels finden sich noch heute in der Kirche, fragen Sie Ihren Reiseführer danach. Früher gab es unter dem Tempel einen Hügel oder ein Grab. In diesem wurden Schmuckstücke aus dem 5. Jahrhundert v. Chr. gefunden, die im Belgrader Geschichtsmuseum aufbewahrt werden. Dies macht dieses bescheidene Denkmal mehr als zweieinhalbtausend Jahre alt.

Wir setzen unsere Tour mit dem Kloster Đurđevi Stupovi fort, das mehr als 800 Jahre alt ist. Es wurde von Stefan Nemanja, dem Stammvater der Nemanjić-Dynastie und des Staates Serbien, gegründet. Mit seiner einzigartigen Architektur und geographischen Lage auf dem Gipfel des Hügels überragt es das gesamte Tal und fesselt die Aufmerksamkeit der Beobachter. Neben der Kirche des Heiligen Georg werden wir auch die Dragutin-Kapelle besuchen. Sie zeigt das Staatsparlament in Ras und enthält eine bemalte Genealogie der Nemanjić-Dynastie.

Wenn Sie möchten, können wir auch zum Kloster Studenica fahren. Es liegt eine Autostunde von Novi Pazar entfernt. Das Kloster ist bekannt als eines der schönsten und vielleicht das schönste Kloster der Nemanjić-Dynastie und ist bekannt für seine Fresken und seine wunderschöne blaue Farbe.

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Wunder der Natur

Eines der bekanntesten Sehenswürdigkeiten auf dem Balkan und in Serbien.

🕒 5h

Boat drive

Molitva Sightseeing Point

Drive to Sjenica

Es ist eine Untertreibung zu sagen, dass die natürliche Schönheit dieses Teils von Serbien unglaublich ist. Die Mäander des Flusses Uvac sind einer der Orte in Serbien, die Sie unbedingt besuchen müssen. Es gibt ein großes Interesse an dieser Tour, nicht nur von inländischen, sondern auch von ausländischen Touristen.

Diese Reise beginnt mit der Fahrt durch die schönsten Teile der Umgebung von Novi Pazar. Es geht um das Pešter-Plateau. Sie werden sich fühlen, als wären Sie nicht in Serbien, sondern in der Mongolei oder Kanada. Sie werden nicht aufhören können, die Landschaften der Höhlen zu genießen.

Bringen Sie einen Hoodie, bequeme Wanderschuhe, Wasser und Ersatzkleidung mit.

Wir verlassen Novi Pazar am Morgen. Nach 40 Minuten unvergesslicher Fahrt machen wir eine Pause im Borovi-Hotel in Sjenica, wo uns ein örtlicher Reiseführer empfängt, der die Boote organisiert.

Pošalji upit

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Podeli

Es ist Zeit für ein unvergessliches Abenteuer aus Wasser, Luft und Eis!

Wir begeben uns zum Ort, um an Bord der Schiffe zu gehen und abzufahren. Sie werden eine unglaubliche Kombination aus dem Duft von Gras, Wald und Wind spüren, die Frische von den nahegelegenen Bergen mit Feuchtigkeit und Wassertropfen vermischt. Schauen Sie nach oben zum endlosen Himmel, der von Gänsegeiern durchschnitten wird, deren Spannweite halb so lang ist wie das Schiff, auf dem Sie fahren. Schauen Sie links und rechts. Sie werden Felsen sehen, auf denen diese prächtigen Vögel oft rasten. Es ist leicht zu denken, dass solch ein Anblick gewöhnlich ist, aber das ist er nicht.

Dies sind die Sehenswürdigkeiten, auf die große Weltenbummler und große Länder der Welt stolz sind. Diesmal sind Sie ein Reisender, der die Größe und Schönheit Serbiens versteht.

(man kann manchmal nicht in die Höhle eintreten, bitte fragen Sie den Organisator) Wir halten an und nehmen die Ausrüstung mit, um in die Höhle zu gelangen. Vergessen Sie nicht, eine Kapuzenjacke oder eine Jacke mitzubringen, da die Temperatur in der Höhle etwa 15 Grad beträgt, unabhängig von der Temperatur draußen. Sobald Sie sich ihr nähern, werden Sie den kalten Atem der Erde spüren und die mystischen Korridore hören, die wir betreten. Die Höhle wird zu Recht die Eishöhle genannt, wegen der Höhlenschmuckstücke, die wie versteinertes Eis aussehen. Sie werden denken, dass Sie durch irgendwelche verborgenen unterirdischen Reiche der Zwerge gehen, wenn Sie durch die hallenartigen Korridore und Hallen gehen.

Beim Verlassen werden Sie vom lächelnden Gesicht des Bootsmanns begrüßt, der Sie zurück zum Ausgangspunkt bringt. Für diejenigen, die mehr Wert auf körperliche Fitness legen, gibt es auch die Möglichkeit, zum Moltva-Aussichtspunkt zu wandern, der einen Blick auf die Mäander bietet, die für immer in Ihren Herzen bleiben werden. Der Aufstieg ist steil, daher wird er nicht für ältere Menschen und Menschen mit Herzproblemen empfohlen. Wir empfehlen, Ersatzkleidung mitzubringen, da Sie sicher schwitzen werden und der Wind am Aussichtspunkt immer weht.

Danach empfehlen wir ein Mittagessen im **Borovi Hotel**.

Pošalji upit

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Podeli

Translation of Bosnian content

Bosnian language	Literal English translation
<p>Meadrima Uvca Jedno od najposećenijih mesta u Srbiji Malo je reći da su prirodne lepote ovog dela Srbije neverovatne. Meandri Uvca su jedno od mesta u Srbiji koje morate posetiti. Za ovu turu postoji ogromno interesovanje, ne samo domaćih već i stranih turista. Ovo putovanje počinje prolaskom kroz najlepše delove okoline Novog Pazara. Radi se o visoravni Pešter. Osećaćete se kao da niste u Srbiji već u Mongoliji ili Kanadi. Nećete moći da prestanete da uživate u pejzažima Pešteri. Ponesite duksericu, udobnu obuću za pešačenje, vodu i rezervnu odeću. Polazimo iz Novog Pazara ujutru. Nakon 40 minuta nezaboravne vožnje pravimo pauzu u hotelu Borovi u Sjenici gde nas dočekuje lokalni vodič koji organizuje brodove. reme je za nezaboravnu avanturu vode, vazduha i leda! Idemo do mesta za ukrcavanje u brodove i polazimo. Osetićete neverovatan spoj mirisa trave, šume i vetra koji donosi svežinu sa obližnjih planina koji se mešaju sa vlagom i notama vode. Pogledaj gore beskrajno nebo koje presecaju beloglavi supovi, čija dužina krila prelazi polovinu broda kojim se vozite. Pogledajte levo i desno, videćete stene na kojima se ove veličanstvene ptice neretko odmaraju. Lako je pomisliti da je takav prizor običan, ali nije. To su prizori kojima se hvale veliki svetski putnici i velike države u svetu. Ovog puta vi ste putnik koji shvata veličinu i lepotu Srbije. Zaustavljamo se i uzimamo opremu za ulazak u pećinu. Ne zaboravite da ponesete duksericu ili jaknu jer je temperatura u pećini oko 15 stepeni, bez obzira na temperaturu vani. Čim joj se približite osetićete hladni dah zemlje u čuje mistične hodnike ulazimo. Pećina se sa pravom zove Ledena pećina zbog pećinskog nakita koje se u njoj nalazi, a izgleda kao okamenjeni led. Pomislićete da ulazite u neko skriveno podzemno carstvo patuljaka kada budete prolazili kroz pećinske hodnike i dvorane. Pri izlasku će vas dočekati nasmejano lice čamdžije koji će vas vratiti na mesto polaska.</p>	<p>Through the Uvac meanders One of the most visited places in Serbia It is an understatement to say that the natural beauty of this part of Serbia is incredible. The meanders of Uvac are one of the places in Serbia that you must visit. There is a huge interest in this tour, not only from domestic but also from foreign tourists. This journey begins with passing through the most beautiful parts of the surroundings of Novi Pazar. It is about the Pešter plateau. You will feel as if you are not in Serbia but in Mongolia or Canada. You will not be able to stop enjoying the landscapes of the Caves. Bring a hoodie, comfortable walking shoes, water and spare clothes. We leave Novi Pazar in the morning. After 40 minutes of unforgettable driving, we take a break at the Borovi hotel in Sjenica, where we are greeted by a local guide who organizes the boats. reme is for an unforgettable adventure of water, air and ice! We go to the place to board the ships and leave. You will feel an incredible combination of the scent of grass, forest and wind that brings freshness from the nearby mountains mixed with moisture and notes of water. Look up at the endless sky cut by griffon vultures, whose wingspan is half the length of the ship you are riding on. Look left and right, you will see rocks where these magnificent birds often rest. It is easy to think that such a sight is ordinary, but it is not. These are the sights that great world travelers and great countries in the world are proud of. This time you are a traveler who understands the greatness and beauty of Serbia. We stop and take the equipment to enter the cave. Don't forget to bring a hoodie or jacket because the temperature inside the cave is around 15 degrees, regardless of the temperature outside. As soon as you approach it, you will feel the cold breath of the earth and hear the mystical corridors we enter. The cave is rightfully called the Ice Cave because of the cave jewelry found in it, which looks like petrified ice. You'll think you're entering some hidden</p>

Postoji i opcija za one vrednije i fizički spremnije za pešačenje do vidikovcima Molitva sa kojeg se pruža pogled na meandre koji će vam večno ostati u srcima. Uspom je strm tako da ga ne savetujemo starijima i onima koji imaju srčanih problema. Savetujemo da donesete i rezervnu odeću, jer će te sigurno oznojiti a na vidikovcu uvek duva vetar. Nakon toga preporučujemo ručak u [hotelu Borovi](#).

Čaršijska tura

Obilazimo najznačajnija mesta u staroj čaršiji Osetite tragove Istanbula, Bagdada, islama i orijenta u uskim ulicama stare čaršije. Neka vam ljubaznost Novopazaraca izmami osmeh i toplinu u srcu. Posetite gradsku tvrđavu i simbol grada [kulu Motrilju](#). [Popijte kafu u hamamu](#) starom skoro šest vekova.

Turisti iz Srbije posebno vole ovu turu jer imaju priliku da uspostave kontakt sa komšijama Bošnjacima. Imaju priliku da posete islamsku bogomolju, bošnjačku sobu i da pitaju sve što žele o bošnjačkoj kulturi i Islamu koja je našalost pod uticajem lažnih vesti i medija ocrnjena i satanizovana. Sastajemo se kod [sebilja ili česme](#) u poznatom orijentalnom izdanju. Ne, nismo kopirali onu iz Baš čaršije – ova je upravo poklon od grada Sarajeva Novom Pazaru. Voda zauzima vrlo važno mesto u Islamu.

Nastavljamo sa obilaskom [Amir-aginog hana](#). Videćete kako izgleda srednjovekovni turski hostel za trgovce.

Dalje prolazimo kroz trg Isa-bega Isakovića, osnivača Novog Pazara pre više od 550 godina. Odatle se pruža neverovatan pogled na [Bedem – simbol grada](#) odnosno deo tvrđave na kojoj se nalazi gradska biblioteka. Uz priču o istoriji Novog Pazara u Osmanlijskom carstvu ulazimo u [gradski park u tvrđavi](#). Videćete [kulu Motrilju](#) koja motri na grad već više od dva veka. Uz to se ona nalazi na grbu grada Novog Pazara.

Iz grada se uskim ulicama probijamo do [Altun-alem džamije](#). Tu ćete čuti [dirljivu priču o Altuni](#), zanosnoj ćerci bega, čiji je život usko povezan sa ovom džamijom. Imaćete priliku da uđete u džamiju, gde će vam vodič pričati o Islamu.

Nakon dodira istoka idemo dalje prema [hamamu ili kupatilu](#) iz šesnaestog veka koji čeka restauraciju. Dok se to ne izvrši u hamamu možete popiti kafu u atmosferi kao nigde u svetu.

Nakon predaha idemo u [gradski muzej](#) gde ćete imati priliku da zavirite u tradicionalne postavke soba – bošnjačke i srpske. Pri tome ćete posvedočiti razlikama i sličnosti ovih dveju tradicija.

underground realm of the dwarves when you walk through the cavernous corridors and halls.

At the exit, you will be greeted by the smiling face of the boatman who will take you back to the place of departure.

There is also an option for those who are more valuable and physically ready to hike to the Molitva lookout, which offers a view of the meanders that will remain in your hearts forever. The climb is steep, so it is not recommended for the elderly and those with heart problems. We advise you to bring spare clothes, because you will surely sweat and the wind is always blowing at the viewpoint.

Afterwards, we recommend lunch at the Borovi Hotel.

City tour

We visit the most important places in the old bazaar. Feel the traces of Istanbul, Baghdad, Islam and the Orient in the narrow streets of the old bazaar. May the kindness of the people of Novopazar make you smile and warm your heart. Visit the city fortress and the symbol of the city, the Motrilje tower. Drink a coffee in a hammam that is almost six centuries old.

Tourists from Serbia especially like this tour because they have the opportunity to establish contact with their Bosniak neighbors. They have the opportunity to visit the Islamic place of worship, the Bosniak room and to ask everything they want about Bosniak culture and Islam, which is unfortunately denigrated and demonized under the influence of fake news and media.

We meet at the sebilja or fountain in the famous oriental edition. No, we did not copy the one from Baš čaršija - this one was a gift from the city of Sarajevo to Novi Pazar. Water occupies a very important place in Islam.

We continue with the tour of Amir-aga's khan. You will see what a medieval Turkish hostel for merchants looks like.

Further on, we pass through the square of Isa-bey Isaković, the founder of Novi Pazar more than 550 years ago. From there, there is an incredible view of the Wall - the symbol of the city, i.e. part of the fortress where the city library is located. With a story about the history of Novi Pazar in the Ottoman Empire, we enter the city park in the fortress. You will see the Motrilja tower, which has been watching over the city for more than two centuries. In addition, it is found on the coat of arms of the city of Novi Pazar.

From the city, we make our way through the narrow streets to the Altun-alem mosque. There you will hear the touching story of Altuna, the ravishing daughter of the bey, whose life is closely connected with this mosque. You will have the opportunity to enter the mosque, where the guide will tell you about Islam.

After touching the east, we continue towards the sixteenth-century hammam, or bathhouse, which is awaiting restoration. Until that is done in the hammam you can drink coffee in an atmosphere like nowhere else in the world.

After a break, we will go to the city museum, where you will have the opportunity to take a look at the traditional settings of the rooms - Bosniak and Serbian. In doing so, you will witness the differences and similarities of these two traditions.

Following the footsteps of Nemanjić

UNESCO: Peter's Church, Đurđevi Stupovi, Sopoćani

Witness the magnificence of Serbian history and cultural heritage of Serbia! This is the cradle where the Republic of Serbia was born, here the Nemanjićs founded the Serbian medieval state on the basis of which today's republic exists. All monuments that are visited in this tour, due to their beauty and history, belong to the world cultural heritage under the auspices of UNESCO. People from all over the

Stopama Nemanjića

UNESCO: Petrova crkva, Đurđevi Stupovi, Sopoćani

Posvedočite veličanstvenost srpske istorije i kulturnog nasleđa Srbije! Ovo je kolevka gde se Republika Srbija rodila ovde su Nemanjići osnovali srpsku srednjovekovnu državu na čijem osnovu postoji današnja republika. Svi spomenici koji se obilaze u ovoj turi, zbog lepote i istorije, pripadaju svetskoj kulturnoj baštini pod okriljem UNESCO-a. Ljudi iz celog sveta dolaze da posete ove jedinstvene spomenike srpske kulture.

U toku ove ture ćete doživeti spomenike hrišćanske srednjovekovne srpske države ([Petrova crkva](#), [manastir Đurđevi stupovi](#) i [manastir Sopoćani](#)) koji predstavljaju bisere sažimanja istoka i zapada u arhitekturi i fresko slikarstvu. Zbog te jedinstvene sinteze ove spomenike posećuju ne samo vernici već i zaljubljenici u istoriju, kulturu i umetnost.

Uz pogled koji uzima dah na planine [Goliju](#), [Rogoznu](#), [Kopaonik](#) i [Peštersku visoravan](#) nastavljamo prema manastiru Sopoćani, jednom od najlepših i jedinstvenih manastira u Srbiji.

Prateći dolinu reke Raške po kojoj je Ras dobio ime, susrećemo se sa ostacima grada Trgovišta i utvrđenja Gradine iznad njega. To naselje ima bogatu istoriju jer podaci govore da su je naseljavali Rimljani, a kasnije bilo važno vojno-strateško utvrđenje.

[Manastir Sopoćani](#) je izgradio kralj Uroš u 13. veku. Odmah će vas zapleniti svojom elegantnošću koja krase jedinstvenu rašku školu arhitekture kojoj pripada. Sopoćani su dobili ime po reči sopot što znači izvor. U blizini se nalazi izvor Raške. Sopoćani su sinteza istoka i zapada. Ukoliko bolje pogledate videćete da spolja liči na zapadne katedrale. Unutrašnjost je vizantijska. Uroš je uposlao najbolje slikare koji su svojim slikarskim umećem nagovestili dolazak Renesanse u Evropi. Freska koja pleni nijansama i umetničkim umećem prikazivanja emocija je Uspeće svete Bogorodice. Tu je još i srpska Mona Liza odnosno freska sv. apostola Filipa koja kao i pomenuto delo Da Vinčija prati pogledom onoga ko je posmatra.

Nakon obilaska Sopoćana preporučujemo odmor ili ručak u idiličnom restoranu [Pazarište](#) gde ćete uz umirujuće zvuke reke Raške i opijajuću pesmu ptica iz obližnje šume uživati u tradicionalnim pazarskim obrocima.

Pre svega tu je [Petrova crkva](#). Na izgled skroman hram, ali sa ogromnim istorijskim i kulturološkim nasleđem. Ova crkva je mesto gde je Stefan Nemanja kršten, oženjen i gde je on predao vlast svom sinu prvom srpskom kralju. U blizini Novog Pazara je boravio i Rastko Nemanjić – Sveti Sava. Crkva Svetog Petra i Pavla je jedna od najstarijih crkvi na Balkanu. Prema zvaničnim podacima datira iz 13. veka. Prema nezvaničnim podacima Petrova crkva je nastala puno pre. Jedna priča kaže da je crkvu osnovao Tit učenik Svetog Pavla i da je on u čast svog učitelja nazvao po njemu.

Petrova crkva je jedan od najstarijih verskih objekata na Balkanu. Ispod ove crkve je pre bila rimski hram. Delove tog hrama možete i danas naći u crkvi, pitajte vodiča.

Ispod hrama je nekada bila humka ili grobnica. U njoj je pronađen nakit iz 5. veka pre nove ere koji se čuva u Beogradu tzv. [Novopazarski nalaz](#). To čini ovaj skromni spomenik starim više od dve i po hiljade godina.

world come to visit these unique monuments of Serbian culture.

During this tour, you will experience the monuments of the Christian medieval Serbian state (Peter's Church, St. George's Column Monastery and Sopoćani Monastery), which represent the pearls of the fusion of East and West in architecture and fresco painting. Due to this unique synthesis, these monuments are visited not only by believers but also by lovers of history, culture and art.

With a breath-taking view of the mountains Golija, Rogozna, Kopaonik and the Pešter plateau, we continue towards the Sopoćani monastery, one of the most beautiful and unique monasteries in Serbia.

Following the valley of the Raška River, after which Ras got its name, we come across the remains of the town of Trgoviste and the fortress of Gradina above it. That settlement has a rich history because the data shows that it was inhabited by the Romans, and later it was an important military-strategic fortification.

The Sopoćani Monastery was built by King Uroš in the 13th century. It will immediately captivate you with its elegance, which adorns the unique Raška school of architecture to which it belongs. The people of Sopot got their name from the word sopot, which means source. The Raška spring is located nearby. Sopoćani are a synthesis of East and West. If you look closely, you will see that it looks like western cathedrals from the outside. The interior is Byzantine. Uroš employed the best painters who, with their painting skills, hinted at the arrival of the Renaissance in Europe. A fresco that captivates with nuances and the artistic skill of depicting emotions is the Succession of the Holy Virgin. There is also the Serbian Mona Lisa, i.e. the fresco of St. of the Apostle Philip, which, like the aforementioned work by Da Vinci, follows the viewer with his gaze.

After visiting Sopoćan, we recommend a rest or lunch at the idyllic restaurant Pazarište, where you will enjoy traditional Pazar meals with the soothing sounds of the Raška river and the intoxicating song of birds from the nearby forest.

First of all, there is Peter's church. A seemingly modest temple, but with a huge historical and cultural heritage. This church is the place where Stefan Nemanja was baptized, married, and where he handed over power to his son, the first Serbian king. Rastko Nemanjić - Sveti Sava also lived near Novi Pazar. The Church of Saints Peter and Paul is one of the oldest churches in the Balkans. According to official data, it dates back to the 13th century. According to unofficial data, Peter's church was built much earlier. One story says that the church was founded by Titus, a disciple of Saint Paul, and that he named it after him in honor of his teacher.

Peter's Church is one of the oldest religious buildings in the Balkans. Below this church was a Roman temple. You can still find parts of that temple in the church today, ask the guide.

There used to be a mound or tomb under the temple. Jewelry from the 5th century BC was found in it, which is kept in the so-called Belgrade. Novopazar find. This makes this modest monument more than two and a half thousand years old.

We continue with the Đurđevi stupovi monastery, which is more than 800 years old. It was founded by Stefan Nemanja, the progenitor of the Nemanjić dynasty and also the state of Serbia. With its unique architecture and geographical position at the top of the hill, it towers over the entire valley and captures the attention of observers. In addition to the Church of St. George, we will also visit the Dragutin Chapel. It depicts the state parliament in Ras. It also contains a painted lineage of Nemanjić.

If you want, we can also go to Studenica monastery. It is located one hour's drive from Novi Pazar. The monastery is known as one of the most beautiful, and perhaps the most

Dalje nastavljamo sa manastriom **Đurđevi stupovi** koji je star više od 800 godina. Osnovao ga je Stefan Nemanja, rodonačelnik dinastije Nemanjića uz to i države Srbije. Svojom jedinstvenom arhitekturom i geografskim položajem na vrhu brda nadvisuje celu dolinu i pleni pažnju posmatrača. Pored crkve Svetog Đorđa, posetićemo i Dragutinovu kapelu. U njoj je oslikan državni sabor u Rasu. U njemu se takode nalazi i oslikana loza Nemanjića. Ukoliko želite možemo otići i do manastira **Studenica**. On se nalazi na jedan sat vožnje od Novog Pazara. Manastir je poznat kao jedan od najlepših, a možda i najlepši manastir Nemanjića poznat o freskopisu i prelepoj plavoj boji.

beautiful monastery in Nemanjića, known for its frescoes and beautiful blue color.

Translation of German content

German language	Literal English translation
<p>Orient Altstadt Tour Das Erleben des orientalischen Geistes der Stadt. Fühlen Sie die Spuren von Istanbul, Bagdad, Islam und dem Orient in den engen Gassen des alten Basars. Möge die Freundlichkeit der Menschen von Novopazar Sie zum Lächeln bringen und Ihr Herz erwärmen. Besuchen Sie die Stadtburg und das Wahrzeichen der Stadt, den Motrilja Wachturm. Trinken Sie einen Kaffee in einem Hamam, das fast sechs Jahrhunderte alt ist.</p> <p>Touristen aus aller Welt schätzen diese Tour besonders, weil sie die Möglichkeit haben, Kontakt mit dem einzigartigen islamischen Erbe in Europa aufzunehmen. Sie haben die Gelegenheit, den islamischen Gebetsraum, den Bosniakenraum, zu besuchen und alles zu fragen, was sie über die bosniakische Kultur und den Islam wissen möchten, der leider unter dem Einfluss von Fake News und Medien verunglimpft und dämonisiert wird.</p> <p>Wir treffen uns am Sebilj oder Brunnen in der berühmten orientalischen Ausgabe. Wasser nimmt im Islam und in Novi Pazar einen sehr wichtigen Platz ein. Es symbolisiert Veränderung und Reinigung – so können Sie sich am Ende der Tour fühlen.</p> <p>Wir setzen die Tour mit dem Amir-Agas Han fort. Dort werden Sie sehen, wie ein mittelalterliches türkisches Gasthaus für Händler aussieht.</p> <p>Weiter geht es durch den Platz von Isa-Bey Isaković, dem Gründer von Novi Pazar vor mehr als 550 Jahren. Von dort aus haben Sie einen ungläublichen Blick auf die Stadtmauer – das Symbol der Stadt bzw. den Teil der Burg, in dem sich die Stadtbibliothek befindet. Mit einer Geschichte über die Geschichte von Novi Pazar im Osmanischen Reich betreten wir den Stadtpark in der Burg. Dort werden Sie den Motrilja Wachturm sehen, der seit mehr als zwei Jahrhunderten über die Stadt wacht. Außerdem ist er auf dem Stadtwappen von Novi Pazar zu finden.</p> <p>Von der Stadt aus machen wir uns auf den Weg durch die engen Gassen zur Altun-Alem-Moschee. Dort hören Sie die berührende Geschichte von Altuna, der bezaubernden Tochter des Beys, deren Leben eng mit dieser Moschee verbunden ist. Sie haben die Gelegenheit, die Moschee zu betreten, wo der Reiseführer Ihnen über den Islam erzählen wird.</p> <p>Nachdem wir den Osten berührt haben, setzen wir unseren Weg fort in Richtung des Hammams aus dem 16. Jahrhundert, das auf seine Restaurierung wartet. Bis dahin können Sie in einer Atmosphäre, wie es sie sonst nirgendwo auf der Welt gibt, Kaffee trinken.</p> <p>Nach einer Pause werden wir zum Stadtmuseum gehen, wo Sie die Gelegenheit haben, einen Blick auf die traditionellen</p>	<p>Orient old town tour Experiencing the oriental spirit of the city. Feel the traces of Istanbul, Baghdad, Islam and the Orient in the narrow streets of the old bazaar. May the friendliness of the people of Novopazar make you smile and warm your heart. Visit the town castle and the town's landmark, the Motrilja watchtower. Sip coffee in a hammam that's almost six centuries old.</p> <p>Tourists from all over the world particularly appreciate this tour for the opportunity to get in touch with the unique Islamic heritage in Europe. They have the opportunity to visit the Islamic prayer room, Bosniak Room, and ask everything they want to know about Bosniak culture and Islam, which unfortunately is being vilified and demonized under the influence of fake news and media.</p> <p>We meet at the Sebilj or fountain in the famous oriental edition. Water occupies a very important place in Islam and in Novi Pazar. It symbolizes change and purification - this is how you may feel at the end of the tour.</p> <p>We continue the tour with the Amir-Agas Han. There you will see what a medieval Turkish merchant inn looks like.</p> <p>Continue through the square of Isa-Bey Isaković, the founder of Novi Pazar more than 550 years ago. From there you have an incredible view of the city walls - the symbol of the city or the part of the castle where the city library is located. With a story about the history of Novi Pazar in the Ottoman Empire, we enter the city park in the castle. There you will see the Motrilja watchtower, which has been watching over the city for more than two centuries. It can also be found on the coat of arms of Novi Pazar.</p> <p>From the city we make our way through the narrow streets to the Altun Alem Mosque. There you will hear the touching story of Altuna, the bey's charming daughter, whose life is closely connected with this mosque. You have the opportunity to enter the mosque where the guide will tell you about Islam.</p> <p>After touching the east, we continue our way towards the 16th century hammam awaiting restoration. Until then, you can sip coffee in an atmosphere unlike any other in the world.</p> <p>After a break we will go to the City Museum where you will have the opportunity to have a look at the traditional interiors of the rooms - Bosniak and Serbian. Along the way, you will experience the differences and similarities between these two traditions.</p>

Einrichtungen der Zimmer – Bosniakisch und Serbisch – zu werfen. Dabei werden Sie die Unterschiede und Ähnlichkeiten dieser beiden Traditionen erleben.

UNESCO Tour

UNESCO-Stätten: Kirche St. Peter, Kloster Đurđevi Stupovi, Kloster Sopoćani

Alle Monumente, die während dieser Tour besucht werden, gehören aufgrund ihrer Schönheit und Geschichte zum Weltkulturerbe unter der Schirmherrschaft der UNESCO. Menschen aus der ganzen Welt kommen, um diese einzigartigen Denkmäler der serbischen Kultur zu besuchen. Während dieser Tour werden Sie die Denkmäler des christlichen mittelalterlichen serbischen Staates (Peterkirche, Kloster Đurđevi Stupovi und Kloster Sopoćani) erleben, die die Perlen der Fusion von Ost und West in Architektur und Freskenmalerei darstellen. Aufgrund dieser einzigartigen Synthese werden diese Denkmäler nicht nur von Gläubigen, sondern auch von Liebhabern von Geschichte, Kultur und Kunst besucht.

Mit einer atemberaubenden Aussicht auf die Berge Golija, Rogozna, Kopaonik und das Pešter-Plateau setzen wir unseren Weg zum Kloster Sopoćani fort, einem der schönsten und einzigartigsten Klöster Serbiens.

Wir folgen dem Tal des Raška-Flusses, nach dem Ras seinen Namen hat, und stoßen auf die Überreste der Stadt Trgoviste und die Festung Gradina darüber. Diese Siedlung hat eine reiche Geschichte, denn die Daten zeigen, dass sie von den Römern bewohnt wurde und später eine wichtige militärisch-strategische Befestigung war.

Das Kloster Sopoćani wurde im 13. Jahrhundert von König Uroš erbaut. Es wird Sie sofort mit seiner Eleganz begeistern, die zur einzigartigen Raška-Schule der Architektur gehört. Die Menschen von Sopot haben ihren Namen von dem Wort Sopot, was Quelle bedeutet. Die Raška-Quelle befindet sich in der Nähe. Sopoćani sind eine Synthese aus Ost und West. Wenn Sie genau hinsehen, werden Sie feststellen, dass es von außen wie westliche Kathedralen aussieht. Das Innere ist byzantinisch. Uroš beschäftigte die besten Maler, die mit ihren Malereikünsten auf die Ankunft der Renaissance in Europa hinwiesen.

Ein Fresko, das mit Nuancen und der künstlerischen Fähigkeit zur Darstellung von Emotionen begeistert, ist die Nachfolge der Heiligen Jungfrau. Es gibt auch die serbische Mona Lisa, das Fresko des Heiligen Apostels Philip, das wie das zuvor genannte Werk von Da Vinci den Blick des Betrachters folgt. Nach dem Besuch von Sopoćan empfehlen wir Ihnen eine Ruhepause oder ein Mittagessen im idyllischen Restaurant Pazarište, wo Sie traditionelle Pazar-Gerichte bei den beruhigenden Klängen des Raška-Flusses und dem betörenden Gesang von Vögeln aus dem nahe gelegenen Wald genießen können.

Zunächst besuchen wir die Kirche des Heiligen Petrus. Eine scheinbar bescheidene Kirche, aber mit einem riesigen historischen und kulturellen Erbe. Diese Kirche ist der Ort, an dem Stefan Nemanja getauft wurde, geheiratet hat und wo er die Macht an seinen Sohn, den ersten serbischen König, übergab. Rastko Nemanjić – Sveti Sava lebte ebenfalls in der Nähe von Novi Pazar. Die Kirche der Heiligen Peter und Paulus ist eine der ältesten Kirchen auf dem Balkan. Offiziellen Daten zufolge stammt sie aus dem 13. Jahrhundert. Nach inoffiziellen Daten wurde die Kirche jedoch viel früher erbaut. Eine Geschichte besagt, dass die Kirche von Titus, einem Schüler des St. Paulus, gegründet wurde und dass er sie zu Ehren seines Lehrers nach ihm benannte.

Die Kirche des Heiligen Petrus ist eines der ältesten religiösen Gebäude auf dem Balkan. Unterhalb dieser Kirche befand sich ein römisches Tempelgebäude. Teile dieses Tempels finden sich noch heute in der Kirche, fragen

UNESCO tour

UNESCO sites: Church of St. Peter, Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery, Sopoćani Monastery

All the monuments visited during this tour are listed as World Heritage Sites under the auspices of UNESCO for their beauty and history. People from all over the world come to visit these unique monuments of Serbian culture.

During this tour you will experience the monuments of the Christian medieval Serbian state (St. Peter's Church, Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery and Sopoćani Monastery) representing the pearls of the fusion of East and West in architecture and fresco painting. Because of this unique synthesis, these monuments are visited not only by believers, but also by lovers of history, culture and art.

With a breathtaking view of the mountains Golija, Rogozna, Kopaonik and the Pešter Plateau, we continue our way to the Sopoćani Monastery, one of the most beautiful and unique monasteries in Serbia.

Following the valley of the Raška River, after which Ras takes its name, we come across the remains of the town of Trgoviste and Gradina Fortress above. This settlement has a rich history, as data shows that it was inhabited by the Romans and later was an important military-strategic fortification.

Sopoćani Monastery was built by King Uroš in the 13th century. It will immediately amaze you with its elegance belonging to the unique Raška school of architecture. The people of Sopot got their name from the word Sopot, which means source. The Raška spring is nearby. Sopoćani are a synthesis of East and West. If you look closely you will see that it looks like western cathedrals from the outside. The interior is Byzantine. Uroš employed the best painters, who with their artistic skills indicated the arrival of the Renaissance in Europe.

A fresco that delights with nuance and artistic skill in depicting emotion is the Imitation of the Virgin. There is also the Serbian Mona Lisa, the fresco of Saint Philip the Apostle, which, like the aforementioned Da Vinci work, follows the viewer's gaze. After visiting Sopoćan, we recommend a rest or lunch at the idyllic Pazarište Restaurant, where you can enjoy traditional Pazar dishes to the soothing sounds of the Raška River and the beguiling songs of birds from the nearby forest.

First we visit the Church of Saint Peter. A seemingly humble church but with a huge historical and cultural heritage. This church is the place where Stefan Nemanja was baptized, got married and where he passed power to his son, the first Serbian king. Rastko Nemanjić – Sveti Sava also lived near Novi Pazar. The Church of Saints Peter and Paul is one of the oldest churches in the Balkans. According to official data, it dates back to the 13th century. However, according to unofficial data, the church was built much earlier. One story has it that the church was founded by Titus, a student of St. Paul, and that he named it after him in honor of his teacher.

The Church of Saint Peter is one of the oldest religious buildings in the Balkans. Below this church was a Roman temple building. Parts of this temple can still be found in the church today, ask your guide about it. There used to be a mound or tomb under the temple. In this, jewelry from the 5th century BC. found in the History Museum of Belgrade. This makes this humble monument more than two and a half thousand years old.

Sie Ihren Reiseführer danach. Früher gab es unter dem Tempel einen Hügel oder ein Grab. In diesem wurden Schmuckstücke aus dem 5. Jahrhundert v. Chr. gefunden, die im Belgrader Geschichtsmuseum aufbewahrt werden. Dies macht dieses bescheidene Denkmal mehr als zweieinhalbtausend Jahre alt.

Wir setzen unsere Tour mit dem [Kloster Đurđevi Stupovi](#) fort, das mehr als 800 Jahre alt ist. Es wurde von Stefan Nemanja, dem Stammvater der Nemanjić-Dynastie und des Staates Serbien, gegründet. Mit seiner einzigartigen Architektur und geographischen Lage auf dem Gipfel des Hügels überragt es das gesamte Tal und fesselt die Aufmerksamkeit der Beobachter. Neben der Kirche des Heiligen Georg werden wir auch die Dragutin-Kapelle besuchen. Sie zeigt das Staatsparlament in Ras und enthält eine bemalte Genealogie der Nemanjić-Dynastie.

Wenn Sie möchten, können wir auch zum [Kloster Studenica](#) fahren. Es liegt eine Autostunde von Novi Pazar entfernt. Das Kloster ist bekannt als eines der schönsten und vielleicht das schönste Kloster der Nemanjić-Dynastie und ist bekannt für seine Fresken und seine wunderschöne blaue Farbe.

Wunder der Natur

Eines der bekanntesten Sehenswürdigkeiten auf dem Balkan und in Serbien.

Es ist eine Untertreibung zu sagen, dass die natürliche Schönheit dieses Teils von Serbien unglaublich ist. [Die Mäander des Flusses Uvac](#) sind einer der Orte in Serbien, die Sie unbedingt besuchen müssen. Es gibt ein großes Interesse an dieser Tour, nicht nur von inländischen, sondern auch von ausländischen Touristen.

Diese Reise beginnt mit der Fahrt durch die schönsten Teile der Umgebung von Novi Pazar. Es geht um [das Pešter-Plateau](#). Sie werden sich fühlen, als wären Sie nicht in Serbien, sondern in der Mongolei oder Kanada. Sie werden nicht aufhören können, die Landschaften der Höhlen zu genießen.

Bringen Sie einen Hoodie, bequeme Wanderschuhe, Wasser und Ersatzkleidung mit.

Wir verlassen Novi Pazar am Morgen. Nach 40 Minuten unvergesslicher Fahrt machen wir eine Pause im [Borovi-Hotel in Sjenica](#), wo uns ein örtlicher Reiseführer empfängt, der die Boote organisiert.

Es ist Zeit für ein unvergessliches Abenteuer aus Wasser, Luft und Eis!

Wir begeben uns zum Ort, um an Bord der Schiffe zu gehen und abzufahren. Sie werden eine unglaubliche Kombination aus dem Duft von Gras, Wald und Wind spüren, die Frische von den nahegelegenen Bergen mit Feuchtigkeit und Wassertropfen vermischt. Schauen Sie nach oben zum endlosen Himmel, der von Gänsegeiern durchschnitten wird, deren Spannweite halb so lang ist wie das Schiff, auf dem Sie fahren. Schauen Sie links und rechts, Sie werden Felsen sehen, auf denen diese prächtigen Vögel oft rasten. Es ist leicht zu denken, dass solch ein Anblick gewöhnlich ist, aber das ist er nicht.

Dies sind die Sehenswürdigkeiten, auf die große Weltbummler und große Länder der Welt stolz sind. Diesmal sind Sie ein Reisender, der die Größe und Schönheit Serbiens versteht.

(man kann manchmal nicht in die Höhle eintreten, bitte fragen Sie den Organisator) Wir halten an und nehmen die Ausrüstung mit, um in die Höhle zu gelangen. Vergessen Sie nicht, eine Kapuzenjacke oder eine Jacke mitzubringen, da die Temperatur in der Höhle etwa 15 Grad beträgt, unabhängig von der Temperatur draußen. Sobald Sie sich ihr nähern, werden Sie den kalten Atem der Erde spüren und

We continue our tour with Đurđevi Stupovi Monastery, which is more than 800 years old. It was founded by Stefan Nemanja, the progenitor of the Nemanjić dynasty and the state of Serbia. With its unique architecture and geographic position on the top of the hill, it dominates the entire valley and captivates the attention of observers. Besides the Church of St. George, we will also visit the Dragutin Chapel. It shows the state parliament in Ras and contains a painted genealogy of the Nemanjić dynasty.

If you wish, we can also go to the Studenica Monastery. It is an hour's drive from Novi Pazar. The monastery is known as one of the most beautiful and perhaps the most beautiful monastery of the Nemanjić dynasty and is known for its frescoes and beautiful blue color.

Wonder of nature

One of the most famous sights in the Balkans and Serbia.

To say that the natural beauty of this part of Serbia is incredible is an understatement. The meanders of the Uvac River are one of the must-visit places in Serbia. There is a lot of interest in this tour not only from domestic but also from foreign tourists.

This journey starts with driving through the most beautiful parts of Novi Pazar surroundings. It's about the Pešter Plateau. You will feel like you are not in Serbia but in Mongolia or Canada. You won't be able to stop enjoying the landscapes of the caves.

Bring a hoodie, comfortable walking shoes, water, and spare clothes.

We leave Novi Pazar in the morning. After 40 minutes of unforgettable ride we will have a break at Borovi hotel in Sjenica, where we will be met by a local guide who will organize the boats.

It's time for an unforgettable adventure of water, air and ice! We head to the place to board the ships and depart. You will feel an incredible combination of the scent of grass, forest and wind, mixing freshness from the nearby mountains with humidity and water drops. Gaze up at the endless sky cut by griffon vultures whose wingspan is half the length of the ship you are sailing on. Look left and right and you will see rocks where these magnificent birds often roost. It's easy to think that such a sight is ordinary, but it isn't.

These are the sights that great globetrotters and great countries of the world are proud of. This time you are a traveler who understands the grandeur and beauty of Serbia. (sometimes you can't enter the cave, please ask the organizer) We stop and take the equipment to enter the cave. Don't forget to bring a hooded jacket or jacket as the temperature inside the cave is around 15 degrees regardless of the temperature outside. As soon as you approach it you

die mystischen Korridore hören, die wir betreten. Die Höhle wird zu Recht die Eishöhle genannt, wegen der Höhlenschmuckstücke, die wie versteinertes Eis aussehen. Sie werden denken, dass Sie durch irgendwelche verborgenen unterirdischen Reiche der Zwerge gehen, wenn Sie durch die hallenartigen Korridore und Hallen gehen.

Beim Verlassen werden Sie vom lächelnden Gesicht des Bootsmanns begrüßt, der Sie zurück zum Ausgangspunkt bringt. Für diejenigen, die mehr Wert auf körperliche Fitness legen, gibt es auch die Möglichkeit, zum Molitva-Aussichtspunkt zu wandern, der einen Blick auf die Mäander bietet, die für immer in Ihren Herzen bleiben werden. Der Aufstieg ist steil, daher wird er nicht für ältere Menschen und Menschen mit Herzproblemen empfohlen. Wir empfehlen, Ersatzkleidung mitzubringen, da Sie sicher schwitzen werden und der Wind am Aussichtspunkt immer weht.

Danach empfehlen wir ein Mittagessen im [Borovi Hotel](#).

will feel the cold breath of the earth and hear the mystical corridors that we enter. The cave is rightly called the Ice Cave because of the cave jewels that look like petrified ice. You'll think you're walking through some hidden subterranean realms of the dwarves as you walk through the hall-like corridors and halls.

Upon exiting you will be greeted by the smiling face of the bosun who will take you back to the starting point. For those who value physical fitness more, there is also the option to hike to the Molitva viewpoint, which offers a view of the meanders that will stay in your hearts forever. The climb is steep, so it is not recommended for the elderly and those with heart problems. We recommend bringing spare clothes as you are sure to sweat and the wind is always blowing at the viewpoint.

Afterwards we recommend lunch at Borovi Hotel.